

UNSTEADY FLOW OF A TRANSONIC TURBINE BLADE WITH SHOCK CONTROL BUMP USING DDES

Weiran Zhang

Department of Energy and Power Engineering
Tsinghua University
Tsinghua, 100084, China

Jian Chen

Department of Energy and Power Engineering
University of Shanghai for Science and Technology
Shanghai, 200093, China

Xinrong Su

Department of Energy and Power Engineering
Tsinghua University
Beijing, 100084, China

Xin Yuan

Department of Energy and Power Engineering
Tsinghua University
Beijing, 100084, China

ABSTRACT

With the continuous increase in turbine load, complex flow structures such as shock wave/boundary layer interaction (SWBLI) inevitably appear in the transonic cascade passage, leading to significant aerodynamic losses. Shock control bumps (SCBs) have been relatively widely explored for applications in both internal and external flow shock control due to their practical and straightforward characteristics. The mechanism through which SCBs influence complex unsteady flow structures is not fully understood, and current Reynolds-Averaged Navier–Stokes (RANS) methods struggle to accurately predict unsteady, multi-scale turbulent flows. Therefore, in this work, an SCB specially designed for a transonic turbine blade is simulated using Delayed Detached Eddy Simulation (DDES), and the underlying mechanisms of the unsteady flow are analyzed. Results show that with the SCB, the shock wave structures inside the cascade passage are significantly altered, and the SWBLI is weakened. Besides, an interesting finding is that the trailing-edge wake is also weakened due to changes in the unsteady flow structures. These contribute significantly to the loss reduction of the transonic blade.

Keywords: Transonic turbine; unsteady flow; shock control bump; DDES

NOMENCLATURE

SWBLI Shock Wave Boundary Layer Interaction
SCB Shock Wave Control Bump
RANS Reynolds Averaged Navier-Stokes
DDES Delayed Detached Eddy Simulation
LES Large Eddy Simulation
DNS Direct Numerical Simulation
DES Detached Eddy Simulation
RBF Radial Basic Function
FFT Fast Fourier Transform
S Shock Wave Function
TKE Turbulence Kinetic Energy
PSD Power Spectral Density
 P Total Pressure
 P_0 Static Pressure
 γ Specific Heat Ratio
 Ma Mach Number
 u', v' Fluctuating Velocity Components

1 INTRODUCTION

In advanced gas turbines and aero-engines, turbine blades are subjected to increasingly aerodynamic loading which lead to a series of issues such as energy loss, pressure drop, and flow

separation caused by shock waves [1]. These problems are becoming increasingly prominent, severely affecting the overall performance and efficiency of the engine. To mitigate the adverse effects of shock waves, SCB were proposed in 1970 and were initially applied in external flow fields. With continuous advancements in SCB technology in recent years, its application has gradually been expanded; however, its application in turbomachinery is less explored. For its applications in transonic flow, the key to SCB's ability to achieve shock attenuation and boundary layer control, thereby reducing cascade passage losses, lies in its implementation of active flow control within the SWBLI region. This mechanism involves complex interactions across multiple spatial and temporal scales and exhibits intricate unsteady characteristics [2]. Therefore, to reveal the active flow restructuring mechanism of SCB through numerical simulation methods, it is necessary to employ high-fidelity numerical simulations to accurately capture the fine-scale structures in the flow field.

Commonly used numerical simulation methods mainly include RANS [3], Large Eddy Simulation (LES) [4], Direct Numerical Simulation (DNS) [5], among others. The RANS method rapidly obtains time-averaged solutions of flow field at a relatively low computational cost; however, it has inherent limitations in turbulence modeling, as it cannot resolve multi-scale turbulent structures and their spatial evolution details, thus making it difficult to capture fine-scale features in the flow field. Garnier et al [6] conducted a numerical study on the bidirectional interaction between an oblique shock wave and a flat plate using the LES method. By comparing the results with experimental data, they demonstrated that LES can effectively predict such physically complex flow phenomena. Meanwhile, Loginov et al [7] also employed the LES method to conduct an in-depth investigation into the flow phenomena and turbulent structures within supersonic boundary layers. Their numerical simulation results directly reproduced the experimental data and observed a periodic shedding phenomenon in the wake of the primary shock. Wheeler [8] employed DNS method to investigate the flow phenomena in a transonic nozzle guide vane, with a focus on analyzing the effects of turbulent dissipation on losses and heat transfer in the trailing-edge region. Although LES and DNS method have been proven effective in simulation complex turbulent flows, in practical applications, due to constraints in computational cost, resources, and time requirements, these two methods remain primarily confined to flows with simple geometries and low Reynolds number conditions.

To apply high-accuracy numerical simulation methods to high-Reynolds-number flows problems with complex geometries, Spalart [9] proposed the Detached Eddy Simulation (DES) method. This approach employs an unsteady RANS model within the near-wall boundary layer and automatically switches to the LES model in regions with strong shear away from wall, significantly improving the utilization efficiency of computational resources. In 2006, Spalart [10] further advances this method by

introducing the DDES method to enhance the simulation capability for stresses. Bian et al. [11] investigated the SWBLI in a high-pressure turbine blade using DDES approach. Their results demonstrate that the DDES method can effectively resolve fine-scale flow structures. In practical applications, while SCB suppress shock waves, they inevitably interfere with other flow structures within the blade rows. Such effects typically involve complex unsteady flow phenomena. Therefore, employing the DDES method, which balances computational accuracy and efficiency, to perform unsteady numerical simulations of the flow field around the SCB and systematically investigate the impact of SCB on loss mechanisms other than shock losses is of significant research and engineering value. This work will help reveal the comprehensive influence mechanism of SCB on flow losses and lay a foundation for improving the aerodynamic efficiency of high-pressure turbine blades.

In this study, a DDES approach was employed to simulate a SCB specifically designed for transonic turbine blades, investigating the shock loss reduction mechanism of the SCB and its impact on wake losses. The results indicate that the SCB significantly alters the shock wave structure within the blade passage and effectively weakens the SWBLI. Furthermore, an interesting finding is that the trailing edge wake is also reduced due to alterations in the unsteady flow structure. These factors simultaneously contribute to a notable reduction of aerodynamic loss for the transonic blade.

This paper consists of five parts. First, the research object and numerical methods are introduced. Next, the influence mechanism of SCB on the steady flow field is analyzed. Subsequently, the effects of SCB on unsteady flow characteristics are examined. Finally, the conclusions are presented.

2 Numerical methods

The primary purpose of this work is to improve the performance of a transonic turbine blade and the design parameters for the baseline blade profile geometry is shown in Table 1. The

Parameter	Value
chord [mm]	72
pitch to chord ration	0.75
stagger angle [degree]	51.9
trailing edge thickness [mm]	1.7
trailing edge wedge angle [degree]	6.4

TABLE 1. Design parameter of the turbine blade

baseline design is perturbed locally using Radial Basis Function in the region with SWBLI and after optimization a new design with local bump is obtained. The blade profile geometry and local detailed features are shown in Fig. 1. As shown in Fig. 1, a

FIGURE 1. Comparison of the blade profile between the baseline design and SCB design.

small bump is added to the suction side and the maximum thickness of the bump is several times of the boundary layer thickness. The streamwise extent of the bump is less than 10% chord length and most part of the blade profile is un-affected.

In this work, a well-proven in-house solver [12, 13, 14, 15, 16, 17] is used to carry out numerical simulation. Turbulent simulation in the RANS mode is based on the Spalart-Allmaras model [18], while in the hybrid RANS/LES simulation, the DDES model is used. For high resolution of turbulent fluctuations, the convective term in the Navier-Stokes equation is discretized using upwind scheme and third-order WENO scheme on the unstructured mesh is employed to reconstruct the variables. Vortex based criterion is adopted to reduce numerical dissipation, which helps to improve the resolution of small-scale structures. In DDES simulation, the baseline upwind scheme is used in the shock wave region and in the rest of the computational domain, with the vortex-based criterion, approximately only 10% of the numerical dissipation in the upwind scheme is employed. For unsteady computation, the dual time-step method is used and the physical time-step is 5×10^{-7} s, which corresponds to about 1000 physical time steps during a flow through period. During each physical time step, the governing equation is solved using an efficient implicit method. Within about 30 iter-

ations, the residual can be dropped by four orders of magnitude.

The computational boundary conditions used in this case are given in Table 2. An unstructured mesh is employed for the

Parameter	Value
Inlet total pressure / Pa	164000
Inlet total temperature / K	440
Outlet static pressure / Pa	81980

TABLE 2. Boundary conditions for numerical simulations at design condition.

computational grid, with 101 grid points evenly distributed along the spanwise direction. The boundary conditions are treated with the Riemann invariants and the outflow boundary surface is positioned at far downstream to minimize the numerical reflections. The dimensionless wall distance of the first layer of mesh points is guaranteed to $y^+ \approx 1$. To resolve important flow structure while maintaining computational efficiency, local grid refinement is applied to critical regions including the SWBLI zone on the suction surface, the bump, the trailing edge, and the wake region based on several preliminary simulations. The final computational mesh consisted of approximately 18 million mesh elements, with details shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 3 shows the experiment [19] and numerical simulation results of the isentropic Mach Number distribution, with good agreement.

3 Loss reduction with SCB

To investigate the effect of SCB on the time-averaged performance, unsteady simulation is conducted for about 10 flow-through periods after the initial transient is diminished to get statistical results. The time-averaged flow is further averaged in the spanwise direction to get two-dimensional results, which are analyzed in this section.

First, the stagnation pressure loss coefficient is compared and it is defined as follows:

$$C_p = \frac{P_{\infty,t} - P_t}{P_t - P_s} \quad (1)$$

In Eqn. 1, $P_{\infty,t}$ represents the inlet stagnation pressure, P_t is the outlet stagnation pressure, and P_s is the outlet static pressure. Besides the design value of outlet Mach number 1.05, the comparison is also conducted over a relatively wide operating range. Fig. 4 shows the stagnation pressure loss coefficients of the SCB

(a) Mesh near the trailing edge

(b) Mesh close to the bump

FIGURE 2. Mesh used for DDES simulation.

blade and the baseline blade under different operating conditions. Within the Mach number range of 1 to 1.12, the aerodynamic efficiency of the SCB blade is significantly higher than that of the baseline blade, demonstrating that the SCB can achieve loss reduction across a relatively wide operational range, thereby effectively improving aerodynamic performance. Particularly at the design condition of $Ma = 1.05$, the stagnation pressure loss coefficient of the shock control bump blade shows a relative reduction of 21% compared to that of the baseline blade.

For typical transonic turbine cascade, the aerodynamics loss mainly occurs in the boundary layer, the wake and the shock wave regions. As the SCB blade differs from the baseline blade only in the small region with bump, it is anticipated that the

FIGURE 3. Comparison of isentropic Mach number between experiment and time-averaged CFD for the baseline case.

FIGURE 4. Stagnation pressure loss coefficient under different outlet Mach number.

boundary loss for both designs should be similar and the loss reduction with SCB should be mainly contributed by the shock region and the wake region. Fig. 5 compares the velocity amplitude of both cases. As shown in Fig. 5 for the baseline design, when the airflow from the suction side and pressure side converges at the endpoint of the trailing edge base region, it forms two swallowtail-shaped waves that propagate downstream, with

(a) Baseline blade profile

(b) Blade profile with SCB

FIGURE 5. Comparison of the velocity amplitude between baseline and SCB.

this convergence point acting as a “source”. The branch on the pressure side interacts with the boundary layer on the suction side of the adjacent blade, generating a reflected shock wave, while the branch on the suction side extends into the downstream flow field and interacts with the wake of the adjacent blade. This results in complex flow structures and significant aerodynamic losses in this region. Fig. 5 shows that with SCB, the shock wave inside the passage can hardly be seen and the suction side branch

is obviously weakened.

Fig. 6 shows the numerical Schlieren for both the baseline blade profile and the SCB blade profile. As can be seen from the comparison, with the control effect of the SCB, the shock wave on the suction surface is transformed from an originally strong normal shock into a series of weak compression waves and oblique shocks. This change is particularly pronounced in the trailing edge region. In terms of shock strength, the shocks generated by the SCB blade profile are significantly weaker than those of the baseline profile. Regarding the shock structure, the shocks in the SCB are noticeably shorter in both the stream-wise and spanwise directions, which substantially reduces the disturbance to the flow field and the entropy generation across the shock wave is obviously reduced.

To quantitatively compare the variations in shock waves and the evolution of the flow structures for different configurations, the shock function is introduced to quantify the shock strength, which is defined as follows:

$$S = \frac{u \cdot \nabla p}{a |\nabla p|} \quad (2)$$

In this formula, u is the velocity vector, ∇p represents the pressure gradient, and a is the local speed of sound. The shock function represents the normal Mach number perpendicular to the shock wave. The magnitude of the shock function value can quantitatively describe the flow structures such as shock waves, expansion waves, and compression waves in a transonic turbine cascade passage.

Fig. 7 shows the comparison of the shock function contour with and without SCB. Through the comparison, various wave system structures within the blade passage can be clearly identified, thereby quantitatively revealing the physical mechanisms behind the changes in velocity and pressure in the flow field. According to the shock wave function analysis, the numerical simulation results clearly show the presence of a strong shock wave and its reflected wave in the middle part of the blade suction surface. In contrast, the SCB result shock function distribution shows no evident reflection wave; instead, a compression wave generated by the protruding windward surface at the midsection of the suction surface is observed, as illustrated in Fig. 7(b). This compression wave induces a pressure increase ahead of the shock wave, thereby effectively controlling the shock intensity.

To further investigate the effect of the SCB on the original shock structure close to the suction surface, Fig. 8 demonstrates the variation of the isentropic Mach number along the blade surface within the normalized axial chord length range of 0.5 to 0.9.

(a) Baseline

(b) SCB

FIGURE 6. Comparison of the numerical Schlieren between baseline and SCB.

(a) Baseline blade profile

(b) Blade profile with SCB

FIGURE 7. Comparison of the shock function between baseline and SCB.

The isentropic Mach number is defined as follows:

$$Ma = \sqrt{\frac{2}{\gamma-1} \left[\left(\frac{P_\infty}{P} \right)^{\frac{\gamma-1}{\gamma}} - 1 \right]} \quad (3)$$

Here, P_∞ represents the total pressure, P represents the static

FIGURE 8. Comparison of the isentropic Mach number along the blade surface in the SWBLI region.

pressure, and γ represents the specific heat ratio. For the baseline profile, a relatively extended favorable pressure gradient first occurs, followed by the emergence of a shock wave around $C_x = 0.71$, accompanied by a strong adverse pressure gradient. In contrast, the pressure distribution of the SCB blade shows that the SCB compresses the airflow between 0.65 and 0.75 to promote pressure recovery and reduce shock strength. Subsequently, between 0.77 and 0.9, the original strong shock structure is replaced by a series of compression and expansion waves. Combined with the shock function values at the trailing edge in the baseline results of Fig. 7(a), it can be observed that the shock at the trailing edge is situated between strong compression and expansion waves. The intense compression as the airflow passes through this region causes an inward concavity in the wake zone.

Fig. 9 compares the velocity distribution on a vertical section immediately adjacent to the trailing edge, with a length equal to half the pitch. Clearly, the SCB significantly increases the velocity in the trailing-edge base region within the normalized length range of 0.2 to 0.5, effectively reducing the velocity deficit in the wake and thereby decreasing wake loss. To further investigate the characteristics and physical mechanisms of SCB's influence on the flow, the following section will focus on analyzing the instantaneous flow field. The velocity deficit across the wake is reduced and thus the mixing loss in the wake region should be smaller. In the literature, SCB is mostly used to control the shock wave for airfoil, for which the trailing edge thickness is very thin and the effect of SCB on the wake is seldom reported. To further confirm this effect, several different transonic turbine blades with SCB have been computed. Results show that when SCB on the

FIGURE 9. Velocity distribution at the trailing edge region before and after shock wave control.

suction side is appropriately designed, similar trend in affecting the wake region can be observed. For the current case, Fig. 10 compares the distribution of the non-dimensional static pressure along the trailing edge. It is evident that the SCB markedly

FIGURE 10. Pressure distribution at the trailing edge before and after shock wave control.

increases the pressure in the trailing-edge base region, achiev-

ing effective pressure recovery. To sum up, the loss reduction of SCB for the current turbine blade is two-fold. First, the shock wave is weakened and the aerodynamic loss in the shock region is reduced. Second, the wake velocity deficit is smaller and the wake loss is also reduced. The latter is seldom reported in the literature. Given the highly unsteady nature of the flow in this region, more analysis will be conducted in conjunction with instantaneous flow results.

4 Effect of SCB on the unsteady flow

In the previous section, the analysis of the time-averaged flow field clearly revealed the mechanism by which the SCB reduces shock wave strength and its influence on downstream cascade loss by altering the flow field structure. The primary advantage of the DDES method lies in its ability to resolve large-scale unsteady vortex structures. To further investigate the unsteady characteristics and physical mechanisms of SCB's impact on the flow, the following section will focus on analyzing the instantaneous flow field.

Fig. 11 compares the instantaneous vortical structures, which are represented by the Q-criterion. The instantaneous vortical structures at a specific instant does not faithfully represent the unsteady behavior of the flow field; however, it can reflect the unsteadiness of the flow field to some extent and from the comparison, it is clear that in addition to the change of the shock wave, the vortical structures for the SCB blade is weaker than the baseline design, which may indicate reduced wake velocity deficit and also reduced wake loss. It has to be noted that for both cases, the mesh elements downstream of the trailing edge are kept the same and have the same resolution of the wake region, thus the difference in this area are mainly caused by SCB.

Two monitoring points are placed in the flow field to observe the unsteady evolutions. The first monitor is closed to the shock control bump and the second is in the wake region. Fluctuating pressure signals during the unsteady simulations are collected and then FFT analysis is conducted to obtain the power spectral density. Fig. 12 shows a comparison of the pressure power spectral densities obtained by the baseline method and the SCB method at two monitoring points. The first monitoring point is close to the bump and from Fig. 12(a), for the baseline design, the unsteady pressure signal is characterized by a series of harmonics. In this case, the SWBLI is not strong enough to trigger flow separation, thus the pressure fluctuation close to the SCB should be caused by the unsteady oscillation of the shock wave front. For the SCB case, the amplitude of these harmonics are obviously smaller. Another monitoring point is positioned inside the wake region and the shedding vortex periodically passes this point. The comparison of PSD at this point is given in Fig. 12(b), it is clear that the fluctuating pressure in the wake region is stronger than the bump region in Fig. 12(a). The harmonic which has the maximum PSD amplitude is related to the shed-

(a) Baseline blade profile

(b) Blade profile with SCB

FIGURE 11. Comparison of the instantaneous vortical structures between the baseline and SCB blades.

ding vortex and it is clear that with SCB the pressure fluctuation due to vortex shedding is obviously reduced. In both Fig. 12(a) and Fig. 12(b), it can be observed that in the low to medium frequency range where $\text{Frequency} \leq 10^3 \text{Hz}$, SCB case shows strong fluctuating pressure and the reason for this phenomenon is left to be explored in the future work.

To quantify the unsteadiness of the flow field, the resolved part of the turbulent kinetic energy is computed from the un-

(a) Monitoring point close to the bump

(b) Monitoring point in the wake region

FIGURE 12. Comparison of the PSD of fluctuating pressure at two monitoring positions.

steady results, which is defined as

$$\text{TKE} = 0.5(\overline{u'u'} + \overline{v'v'}) \quad (4)$$

where u' and v' represent the fluctuating velocity components. It is noted that cascade configuration is used and periodicity is assumed in the spanwise direction, the contribution from w' is rather small and neglected. TKE value non-dimensionalized using the outlet velocity is shown in Fig. 13. From the comparison, it

(a) Baseline blade profile

(b) Blade profile with SCB

FIGURE 13. Comparison of the non-dimensionalized turbulent kinetic energy between the baseline and SCB blades.

is clear that in this case, the flow unsteadiness is mostly located in the wake region and the unsteadiness of the SWBLI region is much weaker. For the SCB case, the TKE is obviously reduced and the peak value is only half of that in the baseline case.

In existing studies, the vortex shedding and vortex transportation in the wake region are found to be closely related to the loss of high-pressure turbine blade [20, 21, 22, 23]. From the above analysis, it is found that with SCB, the unsteadiness in the

wake region is weaker and in the sense of time-averaged flow, the time-averaged velocity deficit shown in Fig. 9 is reduced. This phenomenon should be caused by the increased base pressure along the trailing edge in the SCB case, as shown in Fig. 10. To explain the reason for the increasing of the base pressure, as simple model is proposed, as shown in Fig. 14. The line 1 – 3 de-

FIGURE 14. A simple model for the explanation of the effect of SCB on the base pressure.

notes the pressure-side branch of the shock wave. The reflected shock and the suction-side branch of the shock wave are also shown in this figure. The base region is between point 1 and point 3. Due to the large-scale flow separation in the base region, it can be assumed that $p_1 \approx p_3$. For transonic flow, from the shock relation it is known that static pressure jumps across the shock wave; however, it can be assumed that static pressure is approximately constant in the direction parallel to the shock wave front, i.e., $p_1 \approx p_2$. With SCB, due to the compression effect caused by the front part of the bump, the local static pressure increases. Also, from Fig. 6, in the SCB case point 2 moves upstream to form a normal shock wave. For turbine blade, the static pressure is generally decreasing along the streamwise direction and thus p_2 should increase and so do p_1 and p_3 . Based on this model, it can be explained that with SCB, the static pressure along the trailing edge increases. Thus, the wake velocity deficit and the unsteady flow in the wake region are considerably reduced, which is a possible mechanism of loss reduction, besides the shock wave region.

5 SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

This study employs the DDES method to conduct numerical simulations of a transonic turbine cascade, followed by the analysis about both time-averaged and unsteady results. The time-averaged numerical simulation results indicate that the strong shock wave originally present on the suction surface of the baseline design is replaced by a series of compression and expansion waves, significantly reducing the shock strength. Subsequent analysis of the trailing edge velocity and pressure reveals that the SCB increases the base pressure at the trailing edge, reduces the velocity deficit, and suggests a potential alteration of the unsteady characteristics of the wake. Analysis of the unsteady results, including turbulent kinetic energy and power spectrum density, demonstrates improvements in the unsteady performance of the wake region. A simplified model is proposed to explain the increase of the base pressure in the SCB case. To sum up, from this work it is shown that SCB can help to reduce aerodynamic loss of transonic turbine blade and the loss reduction mechanism are two-fold. The effect of SCB on the wake region is seldom reported in the literature and more analysis are necessary for further explanation, which are left for future work.

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